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PANDEMIC AND UNCHARTED NEW NORMAL: MOOCS, SERIOUS GAMES AND ONLINE LEARNING COMMUNITIES TO SUPPORT HYBRID CLASSROOMS

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ABSTRACT

The paper outlines the INSYSTED pedagogical framework and the participatory process based on actual university courses that led to it.

It will then discuss the relevance of the INSYSTED pedagogical framework to the European context. To this end, the paper takes stock of current developments by integrating insights from a variety of sources in terms of research and grey literature, complemented with the outcomes of targeted contacts with teachers. In many universities the pandemic led to hybrid delivery modes, with some students attending in the classroom and others participating at the same time remotely online, basically via videoconference; this resulted in an online extension of the physical classroom that blurs the boundaries between physical and online learning spaces.

Finally, the paper will elaborate some key points to give an account of available information, so that it feeds into instructions to operationalise the INSYSTED pedagogical framework. The aim is to maximise the relevance of this approach to the current pandemic and to the uncharted “new normal”.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This paper explores the added value of using MOOCs, serious games and forum-based online learning communities in view of the developments boosted in higher education by COVID-19 pandemic. The aim is to make the most of the pedagogical framework developed by the EU-funded INSYSTED project (Giannatelli & Tomasini, 2020), whose distinctive features are instrumental in promoting student-centred approaches suited to foster soft and digital skills and internationalisation, with a special focus on industrial and management engineering education.

That is what happened in a nutshell: the vast majority of European universities closed their campuses in March 2020 and moved online in April and May due to the COVID-19 crisis: according to the European University Association (2020), 95% pivoted to distance learning throughout the institution. This sudden and unplanned shift to online learning has led faculty and non-academic staff to use new tools, even if already in 2013 almost all higher education institutions offered some kind of digitally enhanced learning (Gaebel et al., 2021).

HEIs and international organisations published online resources to manage teaching and learning during COVID-19³. The situation seemed to be exceptional but transitory, with a response to the unpredictable circumstances that could not always be aligned with the usual quality of pedagogy (Hodges et al., 2020); currently HEIs are experiencing adjustment and systematization to handle the prolonged pandemic with a view to post-COVID recovery.

2 DESIGN AND RATIONALE

This paper investigates the elements that are emerging as pivotal to operationalise the integration of MOOCs, serious games and forum-based online learning communities into curricular higher education in a blended learning setting: the aim is to reasonably maximise the relevance of the INSYSTED approach both to the current COVID-19 crisis and to the uncharted “new normal”.

As the situation has not stabilised yet, the paper takes a pragmatic approach and surveys a variety of relevant sources in terms of research and grey literature such as reports and tutorials, complemented with the outcomes of targeted direct contacts and ad-hoc consulting to faculty during the pandemic. Special attention is devoted to literature regarding the European context produced after the pandemic outbreak.

By reviewing evidence and insights, the paper takes stock of current developments that have an impact on the integration of MOOCs, serious games and forum-based online learning communities in the wake of COVID-19. The pivotal elements

³ Examples include European University Association (EUA), [Resources for digital learning and teaching during the coronavirus pandemic](#); Resources for online teaching from European universities <https://empower.eadtu.eu/coronacrisis>; Educause <https://library.educause.edu/topics/information-technology-management-and-leadership/covid-19>, but also Commonwealth of Learning (COL), UNESCO, OCDE.

surveyed in the paper are expected to feed into the operationalisation of the INSYSTED pedagogical framework in the following project outputs.⁴

3 THE INSYSTED APPROACH

The INSYSTED approach was devised to be flexible so that it can be applied to a whole course, a course section or a single lesson; it aims to support the design from scratch and the (re)design of learning opportunities by blending face-to-face instruction with online activities underpinned by these pillars: MOOCs, serious games and forum-based online learning communities. The pillars can make students engage more actively, so that they foster their soft and digital skills and develop their ability to act in ways that resemble those of experts in the engineering field (authentic learning), hence increasing their preparedness for the challenges of a rapidly evolving labour market.

A distinctive feature of the INSYSTED approach is that it leverages the expertise of Alliance4Tech partner universities in defining relevant Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs) that students are expected to achieve in order to direct the (re-)design of learning opportunities: ILOs are based on actual university courses and can refer not only to the knowledge and skills concerning course topics, but also to soft and digital skills that are somewhat implied.

The challenges emerged from the pandemic give value to the INSYSTED approach because:

- soft and digital skills were proven to be crucial to make the most of digitally-enabled courses that ensure teaching continuity; actually according to a questionnaire to institutional leadership for EUA DIGI-HE project (Gaebel et al., 2021), digital skills are not fully embedded in the compulsory offer of HEIs but need to be reckoned with in curricula and learning outcomes for a more systematic use of digital learning; considering students per se as digitally competent is misleading, as some of them have only limited experience in digital learning (Steffens et al., 2017; Aristovnik et al., 2020);
- the prolonged pandemic sparked universities' reflection on renewed models of internationalisation at home (Coimbra Group, 2020);
- MOOCs, serious games and forum-based online learning communities can offer sustainable ways to complement internationalisation as they are accessible independently of physical location.

In addition to that, students that are accustomed to learner-centred approaches seemed to cope better with the digital semester during the pandemic in Germany (German Centrum für Hochschulentwicklung - CHE, 2020); literature review suggests that student-centred learning approaches are promising at the cross-roads

⁴ The INSYSTED project (<http://www.alliance4tech.eu/insysted/>) is expected to develop staff training events and a manual for faculty and non-academic staff to support longer term integration strategies of MOOCs, serious games and forum-based online learning communities in an international context.

between mathematics and engineering education and that the actual use of videos of online courses and simulations by engineering students is a direction for future research (Pepin et al., 2021). Recent research (Campos et al., 2020; Langer et al., 2021) explores the use of serious games in the areas of engineering, science, and management in on-campus, online and blended settings in Europe.

4 BLENDED AND HYBRID LEARNING

Operationally we can define “blended” a course that is designed so that some in-class time is substituted by equally meaningful online activities, with online components being not an addition to the full course load but a purposeful substitution of some in-class activities⁵.

Blended learning can be operationalised with different levels of sophistication, but it is important to consider that its very context evolved during the pandemic: course delivery modes serving both on-campus and online students gained momentum, with some students attending in the classroom and others participating at the same time remotely online, basically via videoconference. These modes are generally referred to as hybrid learning; they caught on due to COVID-19, as they allow to reduce the number of people in the classroom as a sanitary precaution, and support participation of persons with a condition preventing them from on-campus attendance.

“Blended” and “hybrid” are complex and blurred concepts that were and sometimes are still used as synonyms: in the INSYSTED approach “hybrid” refers mainly to the modalities of accessing classes, with learners alternating between on-campus and online participation modes at the same time with various degrees of choice (Irvine, 2020; The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education, 2020; Beatty, 2019). In this new context “hybrid” indicates constituents distinctively at once, changing the notion of learning space (Cohen et al., 2020). Generally in French this concept is designated as *formation comodale* (“apprentissage hybride” means blended learning); in German as *Hybrid-Lehre* or *hybride Lehre*; at Politecnico di Milano it is referred to as *classe estesa*.

There are variations to how hybrid learning works, with options in-between, such as the instructor deciding that groups alternate on campus so that all students participate in person to some classes, or students choosing each week which modality suits them best. Terms such as blended synchronous, mixed-mode, dual-mode, multi-modal, multi-access, synchromodal, hybrid-flexible (HyFlex) / comodal, Here or There (HOT) share the notion of instruction which combines online and on-campus students at the same time.

By way of illustration, due to the pandemic the University of Edimburgh outlined some bare-bones prototypes for hybrid teaching (Bayne, 2020), Université Toulouse

⁵ <https://tlss.uottawa.ca/site/what-is-a-blended-course>

III published hybrid learning scenarios (Université Toulouse III, 2020) and Universität Göttingen described some operational options to organise student attendance⁶.

It is worth noting that students are experiencing a wide variety of disruptions, as some of them are not on campus anymore and are connecting from environments that might not be conducive to learning because of defective equipment and no high-quality internet connection; furthermore some international students have returned home, in countries sometimes in different timezones and/or with limited or blocked access to foreign internet tools.

Due to the above-mentioned context, this paper outlines the implications for classes that accommodate students participating in diverse modalities, especially on-campus and online at the same time (hybrid synchronous learning).

5 INSYSTED IN CONTEXT

Let's explore how the INSYSTED approach can be fine-tuned for hybrid synchronous learning by considering the emerging pivotal elements to take the synchronous / asynchronous dichotomy beneficially on board:

- equity in course participation;
- student engagement;
- balance between synchronous and asynchronous interaction.

5.1 Equity in course participation

As literature seems to argue, it is crucial to ensure that students have access to an equitable learning experience independently of the modality they are using to access it. That implies to cater for the needs of both students that are on campus and students that participate online synchronously. Actually it is worth considering that teaching on-campus and remote students at the same time requires preparation and organisation as it entails multitasking: instructors need not only to teach on-campus and online students at the same time, but also to operate technology and facilitate interaction between the two cohorts; typically a crucial issue is to manage the audio in the physical space so that those participating via video conferencing can hear properly. Some tools allow to create sub-meetings within a videoconference meeting for smaller groups of participants to collaborate and have discussions (breakout rooms). A study from Malmö university (Leijon & Lundgren, 2019) outlines some challenges in terms of teacher communication within the different spaces and physical interactions within the campus room.

The workload for teachers to prepare lessons might be considerably higher than for usual in-person formats (Seyfeli et al., 2020): more detailed planning is needed to design the possible interactions among the different cohorts of students and among students and materials. One way to mitigate the load on individual teachers is to employ one or more teaching assistants (Bower et al., 2015).

⁶ <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/632946.html#collapse-info-2-01>

As an emerging practice, hybrid synchronous education especially needs to be increased empirical investigation to complement the qualitative case studies (Raes et al., 2019). An Australian research on dual mode approach amongst students undertaking a statistics course in an Australian university, face-to face against online study (Soesmanto & Bonner, 2019), found no significant difference in academic performance, achieved through consistent course delivery and teaching strategies. Another study (Binnewies & Wang, 2019) reports the HyFlex course design used at two campuses of an Australian university, emphasizing the design factors and instructional practices successfully implemented to assure student equity and student engagement in the learning process.

Examples of strategies recommended in European universities to help students keep at pace include providing (e.g. on the LMS) a course schedule with associated tasks and deliverables expected from students (Wylie et al., 2020) and providing a weekly outline/summary with key points to remember and links to assigned readings and resources (École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, 2020a).

Considering all of that, to make the most of the INSYSTED approach also in a hybrid context, it is important to identify the ILOs and the Teaching Learning Activities to achieve them that can be (re)used across on-campus and off-campus participation modes, with a portion carried out asynchronously, such as question-and-answer sessions in class upon previous exposure to targeted MOOC content at home, mindmapping or diagram-labelling tasks or peer evaluation activities launched in class and to be completed asynchronously in the forum-based online learning community, exercises to apply knowledge through the serious game.

5.2 Student engagement

Student engagement is integral to the INSYSTED approach as it supports active learning pedagogies where learners participate in the instructional process beyond listening and taking notes. Nevertheless, promoting engagement in a hybrid setting deserves some scrutiny. Dietrich et al., 2020 present the lessons learned from the feedback from students and teachers who participated in the lockdown semester of two different groups of a 5-year program in Chemistry, Environment and Chemical Engineering at INSA Toulouse (France): considering international students, who were more isolated and less equipped than most other students; unlocking new technologies and quizzes during videoconferences to motivate learners, offering regular question/answer sessions to guide students or give and receive feedback and implementing support materials such as videos so that students can apply their knowledge before the final assessment. Similar suggestions also emerge from Raes literature review (Raes et al., 2019).

Providing opportunities for learners to give peer feedback is also an effective way of empowering and motivating students and, if properly designed, to reduce teacher workload (Wylie et al., 2020). Some research in collaborative group assessment seems to suggest that students are capable of judging peers' performance accurately when the mark is not counted towards the final grade, but tend to be

overly generous when their mark is counted towards their final grade (Sridharan et al., 2019). Louvain learning lab offers some reflections about promoting active behaviours in students by expecting “visible productions” from them, that require to manipulate information (e.g. by taking notes on a video and writing a summary), to transform it (e.g. by synthesising a video, organising it in a chart /mindmap), to discuss/debate it (e.g. by highlighting the links / implications of a specific topic for professional life) (Docq, 2020). Louvain learning lab provides additional food for thought with the ICAP model (Chi & Wylie, 2014) which connects the engagement modes of students with their learning level, gradually going from surface learning to in-depth learning. This model enables instructors to fine-tune the design of teaching activities and to have a more global overview of cognitive engagement modes they can elicit in their students.

Other examples of strategies recommended in European universities to keep students engaged entail scheduling weekly live sessions for students to ask their questions (École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, 2020a) and setting milestones (such as regular submission of exercises, or mid-term take home tests) to give feedback on learning. Choosing questions that are complex enough so that answers are not already available online because they have multiple correct answers, which require some written explanation, or which use freshly available datasets reduces the risk of cheating in an unsupervised setting (École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, 2020b).

5.3 Balance between synchronous and asynchronous interaction

As the hybrid setting serves on-campus and online students, it is important to balance distance online collaboration in synchronous mode during classes, that implies a risk of cognitive overload, and in asynchronous mode, that is conducive to developing responsibility and autonomy by students. Some research in blended synchronous learning highlights the importance of designing for active learning and possible challenges related to heightened levels of cognitive load for teachers and students (Bower et al., 2015).

Examples of strategies include using asynchronous communication tools such as discussion forums to increase students’ engagement (McGee & Reis, 2012) and to scaffold knowledge construction activities through communication with and among students that is permanently available for consultation.

Zydney et al. (2019) suggest to build hybrid synchronous sessions upon asynchronous activities (e.g. readings or performing exercises) from a flipped classroom approach, which lends itself because of the duality of places and modes it implies (in class / at home; synchronous/asynchronous). A concrete example of synchronous session is reported by Heiss and Oxley (Heiss & Oxley, 2021) from a quantitative analysis course where teamwork activity on different portions of a multi-part question has been conducted assigning different roles to each team member to increase engagement.

However, a US-based research (Muñoz et al., 2021) claims that many students in flipped classes during the pandemic have difficulty with self-regulation and keeping up with course materials without a grade incentive; many low-stakes grade incentives interspersed throughout the course can ensure that students learn and benefit from engaging with course materials throughout the term.

Research (Bower et al., 2014; Bower et al., 2015) suggests that permitting backchannel communication during synchronous sessions, by using a live feed (e.g. videoconference text chat) enables everyone to ask their questions and to see other students' questions, with multiple simultaneous non-interfering contributions; strategies to visually identify questions from the rest of the live feed can be used and students can be asked to answer their peers, hence potentially fostering peer interaction within and across attendance modes and reducing the instructor's burden.

The INSYSTED approach supports the combination of synchronous activities with asynchronous activities through the forum-based online learning community; again, accurate planning is needed to reckon with the implications of synchronous activities with students participating both in person and online at the same time.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND TAKE-HOME MESSAGES

How will higher education move forward after the pandemic? It is far too early to come to a conclusion, but it is possible to identify some hints for further in-depth reflection. The exploration of the practices that are gaining momentum during the pandemic seems to suggest that the INSYSTED approach is beneficially adaptable to the new paradigms of course delivery.

Considering the sources surveyed in this paper, blended learning formats are here to stay and to be extended (Bergan et al., 2021; European Higher Education Area and Bologna Process, 2020), as long as they cater for more individualised and flexible learning opportunities complementing in-person teaching and international student mobility (Coimbra Group, 2020; Hudzik, 2020); other prospective elements include increased focus on the flipped classroom and on learning spaces (Farnell et al., 2021; Ackeren, 2020).

Equity in course participation, student engagement and balance between synchronous and asynchronous activities are pivotal in integrating the INSYSTED approach into a hybrid setting; nevertheless ad-hoc reflection and further investigation are needed to calibrate them according to each specific context: as context is key, no size fits nobody.

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